

Short communication

Human perception of Parkinson's disease body odor in comparison to the volatile organic compounds of Parkinson's disease

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: Patients with Parkinson's Disease (PD) have a distinctive body odor, which was first described by a patient's wife as musky and strong. Later analysis of sebum of patients with PD revealed four volatile organic compounds (VOC) (perillic aldehyde, hippuric acid, eicosane, octadecanal), that differed from healthy subjects, and the patient's wife confirmed that three of them smelled like patients with PD. However, it is unclear whether other people can also perceive this PD body odor and whether it can be artificially recreated. Hence, we aimed to systematically assess whether young women can perceive the PD body odor and whether they can discriminate between the PD body odor and the "artificial PD odor" composed of the four VOCs mentioned above.

Methods: T-shirts were collected from 19 people with idiopathic PD and 15 age- and gender-matched healthy participants to represent the PD body odor and the healthy body odor, respectively. The four VOCs were diluted in 1,2-propanediol to prepare the artificial PD body odor. Body odors were rated by 26 young women.

Results: PD body odor was perceived as more musty, strong, smelly, and unpleasant compared to healthy and artificial PD body odor. Furthermore, around 80 % of women were able to discriminate PD body odor from artificial PD body odor.

Conclusion: Overall, this study confirmed a distinctive body odor quality of patients with PD, which can be perceived by young women. However, the four VOCs, composing the artificial PD body odor, were insufficient to reproduce the body odor from PD patients.

1. Introduction

Parkinson's Disease (PD) is the second most common neurodegenerative disease, which is diagnosed clinically after development of motor symptoms such as resting tremor, rigidity, bradykinesia, and postural instability. However, PD develops years before and early detection could be beneficial [1]. A change in body odor ("PD BO") could be of use as an early symptom of imminent PD because it reportedly changes years before the motor symptoms develop. This phenomenon has been first observed by a patient's wife, who was able to discriminate between 6 samples from PD patients and 6 healthy

individuals with 100 % accuracy. Interestingly, she identified one control as a PD patient, however, he was later also diagnosed with PD [2]. According to their preliminary experiments, the PD BO seems to be most prominent in areas with high sebum production, namely in the upper back [2,3]. PD BO could therefore be attributed to the altered sebum composition. Sebum analysis in 2019 found four volatile organic compounds (VOC) (perillic aldehyde, hippuric acid, eicosane, octadecanal), which differed among sebum samples of PD patients and healthy people [3]. Perillic aldehyde was significantly lower, whereas eicosane was significantly higher in PD patients compared to healthy people. Hippuric acid and octadecanal were not significantly different yet trended to be

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higher. To confirm the importance of this finding, the experimentee from Morgan et al. was asked to smell the VOCs from an odor port of a gas chromatography-mass spectrometry. She identified the three VOCs (hippuric acid, eicosane, and octadecanal) as similar to the musky PD BO [3]. However, not much is known about human PD BO perception in general.

Overall, the present study aimed to systematically assess, whether young women can perceive PD BO and whether they can discriminate between PD BO and artificial PD BO composed of the four VOCs (perillic aldehyde, hippuric acid, eicosane, octadecanal).

2. Methods

2.1. Body odor donors and human raters

Body odors were collected from PD patients and healthy age- and gender-matched BO donors. Furthermore, young women were recruited as human raters. Participants gave informed written consent. The study was performed in accordance with the Declaration of Helsinki and approved by the Ethics Committee at the University Clinic of the TU Dresden (application number: BO-EK-548112021).

PD patients were recruited at the Department of Neurology (Faculty of Medicine Carl Gustav Carus). Main inclusion criterion was idiopathic parkinsonism (diagnostic criteria in the Supplement). Exclusion criteria were a COVID-19 infection at the time of recruitment, renal diseases, and inability to participate in the study, e.g. due to movement restriction.

Healthy BO donors were age- and gender-matched and recruited via verbal propaganda. Exclusion criteria were pregnancy, smoking, and significant health restrictions (e.g. pronounced renal insufficiency, PD).

Human raters were recruited via verbal propaganda. To reduce the variance among the raters female participants aged 18–40 years were included. Additionally, only participants, who were familiarized with the PD BO as a part of another BO study were included. In the end of this previous study, they were told which bottle represented the PD BO. Exclusion criteria were pregnancy, smoking, and significant health disorders that may interfere with olfactory function (e.g., diabetes mellitus, renal insufficiency, neurodegenerative diseases such as PD).

2.2. Body odors

BO donors were asked to wear a pre-washed cotton T-shirt for one night following a strict protocol as explained in the Supplement. Next, the back collar of the T-shirts was cut out, and stored individually in plastic bags in a freezer at $-20\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ [4]. BOs were presented in six 500 ml brown bottles. All 15 T-Shirt pieces of healthy participants were put in one bottle (healthy BO) and all 19 T-Shirt pieces of PD patients in the second bottle (PD BO) to reduce the influence of individual BO and to enhance BO stimulus. Next, artificial PD BO was prepared by mixing 10 μM of each of the VOCs (perillic aldehyde, hippuric acid, eicosane, and octadecanal, Supplement Table S1) with 1,2-propanediol. Four bottles of artificial PD BO were prepared, each containing 15 ml of the mixture on a gauze pad. Pieces of a blank odorless pre-washed T-shirt were added. To equalize the background odors, a gauze pad with 15 ml of 1,2-propanediol was added to the healthy BO and PD BO as well. A detailed protocol for BO collection and sample preparation can be found in the Supplement.

2.3. Human ratings

For human ratings there were two appointments to reduce olfactory fatigue. At the first appointment, olfactory function was assessed using the Sniffin' Sticks battery with threshold (T), discrimination (D), and identification (I) summed in the TDI score [5]. Additionally, raters were familiarized with the PD BO by smelling BO from PD patients and healthy age- and gender-matched controls as part of another study.

At the second appointment, raters underwent qualitative and quantitative BO evaluation. For the quantitative part, two discriminations tasks were performed. In the qualitative part, each BO was described using the description matrix and perceptual descriptors. In the end, some of the participants underwent the quantitative part again.

2.4. "Qualitative part"

In the qualitative part, participants were individually presented with three bottles in the same order. They started with the healthy BO, followed by the PD BO, and the artificial PD BO. They were asked to select the words that best described the presented BO from a description matrix [6]: biting, flowery, deodorized, subtle, foul, fresh, moist, individual, cold, musty, natural, neutral, salty, clean, sour, sweaty, strong, pungent, smelly, sweet, unpleasant, warm. These twenty words are the most common words used to describe human BOs among German people [6]. In the end, they were asked to rate the odor on a visual analog scale (VAS) from »not at all« to »very« using the following descriptors: pleasant, intense, and familiar. Furthermore, they had to rate how much distance they wanted from the person whose BO was presented on a scale from »very much« to »none«.

2.5. "Quantitative part"

In the quantitative part, participants had to discriminate the different BO in two 3-alternative forced choice (3-AFC) tasks. In both tasks, three bottles were presented. Each bottle was presented 2 cm from the nose for around 2 s. Participants were blinded. In the end, they were asked to choose the different odor from the three samples in a forced choice manner. There were three rounds per task. In the first discrimination task, two bottles contained artificial PD BO and one contained healthy BO. In the second discrimination task, two bottles contained artificial PD BO and one contained PD BO.

2.6. Statistical analysis

Statistical analysis was performed using R Statistical Software [7] (version 4.2.2; R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria). Detailed information can be found in the Supplement.

3. Results

BO was collected from 15 healthy people and 19 people with PD. There was no difference regarding age or gender among the healthy people and people with PD (Supplement Table S2). For BO ratings, 26 young women were included (Supplement Table S3).

3.1. "Qualitative part"

In the qualitative part, participants were asked to rate each sample. Firstly, they had to choose words that best describe a certain odor using a description matrix. As can be seen on Fig. 1 and Supplement Table S4, PD BO was described as more musty, strong, smelly, and unpleasant compared to the artificial PD BO and healthy BO, indicating that young women were able to perceive the distinctive quality of the PD BO. On the other hand, the artificial PD BO was described as more neutral, and clean compared to the PD BO and healthy BO. Secondly, perceptual descriptor ratings on a VAS for the three samples are shown in Supplement Table S5. PD BO was perceived as less pleasant compared to the artificial PD BO and the healthy BO, whereas there was no difference in odor intensity, familiarity, or preferred distance.

3.2. "Quantitative part"

In the quantitative part, participants underwent two discrimination tasks. Here, 2 or 3 out of 3 correct answers were considered a cut-off for

Fig. 1. Word clouds presenting the words chosen from the description matrix for healthy (Healthy) body odor (BO) in purple, Parkinson’s Disease (PD) BO in orange, and artificial PD BO (ArtPD) in blue. All words that were chosen at least once are shown. The word cloud in the middle shows the first 10 words that differed in their chosen frequencies, colors corresponding to the BO. Those that were significantly different among the three BOs are marked with *. The exact frequencies and comparison is shown in the Supplement Table S4.

For the three word clouds presenting the three BOs, the size of the text corresponds to the number of times the descriptor was used for this BO and does not correspond to the significant differences among the three samples.

participants, who were able to distinguish the different sample. Interestingly, more than 80 % of participants were able to distinguish PD BO from artificial PD BO (Table 1). On the other hand, only around 50 % of participants were able to distinguish healthy BO from artificial PD BO. Participants who could discriminate the BOs had a significantly better olfactory function measured using the TDI score (Supplement Fig. S1).

Table 1

The two discrimination tasks. Discrimination of the different sample using two bottles with artificial PD body odor and one with healthy body odor (healthy) or PD body odor (PD). The olfactory function of participants, who could discriminate, and participants, who could not, is also reported.

Round [^]	Participants who	Healthy N (%)	TDI Median (25 %–75 %)	PD N (%)	TDI Median (25 %–75 %)
1 (N = 26)	Discriminated	12 (46 %)	39.3 (36.7–40.4) ^b	21 (81 %) ^a	37.3 (34.8–39.5) ^a
	Did not discriminate	14 (54 %)	33.9 (31.5–35.6) ^b	5 (19 %) ^a	33.5 (30.5–34.3) ^a
2 (N = 19)	Discriminated	10 (53 %)	36.1 (34.3–39.9)	17 (89 %) ^b	35.0 (34.3–39.5)
	Did not discriminate	9 (47 %)	35.0 (33.5–37.5)	2 (11 %) ^b	34.1 (32.3–35.9)
1 & 2 (N = 19)	Discriminated	6 (32 %)	39.8 (37.8–41.3) ^a	13 (68 %) ^a	37.3 (34.8–40.0)
	Did not discriminate	6 (32 %)	34.3 (31.3–35.6) ^a	1 (5 %) ^a	30.5

Participants who answered 2 or 3 out of 3 correctly, could discriminate the different sample. Others could not.

^a p value < 0.05.

^b p value < 0.001.

[^] The discrimination task was performed by all 26 participants (first round) and additionally by 19 out of 26 participants (second round). The 1 & 2 shows the number of participants who could discriminate or could not discriminate in both rounds.

Next, the expected (random) binominal distribution was calculated. This is the distribution one would expect if participants randomly chose the “different” bottle. Then our distribution was compared to the expected binominal distribution (Supplement Table S6). The distribution of healthy BO discrimination was not significantly different from the expected distribution in both rounds. On the other hand, the distribution of PD BO discrimination differed compared to the expected distribution in both rounds indicating that our group of young females was able to distinguish PD BO from the artificial PD BO.

4. Discussion

We systematically assessed whether young women can perceive the PD BO and whether they are able to discriminate PD BO from artificial PD BO composed of four VOCs (perillic aldehyde, hippuric acid, eicosane, octadecanal). This study confirmed a distinctive BO in PD patients perceived by young women. However, the four VOCs, composing the artificial PD BO, were insufficient to reproduce it.

Patients with PD have a distinctive BO, which the experimentee from Morgan et al. described as strong and musky [2,3]. Here, PD BO was perceived as more unpleasant, strong, smelly, and musty than healthy or artificial PD BO. Musky was not included in the description matrix because it is not part of the validated assessment of BO [6], whereas strong was also used by our raters. Noteworthy, only young women, who were previously familiarized with the PD BO, were included.

The artificial PD BO included four VOCs, which were significantly (or at least trending to be) different in sebum of PD patients compared to healthy people [3]. Here, the PD BO was easily discriminated from the artificial PD BO indicating that using only these four VOCs is not sufficient to reproduce the PD BO - although they might contribute to the unique PD BO [3]. BOs are complex mixtures, and further VOCs are likely needed to reproduce the PD signature. This is in line with the experimentee from Morgan et al., who rated the VOC samples with the addition of the healthy sebum as more familiar to the PD BO compared to the VOC samples without the addition of the healthy sebum [2,3]. Another potential explanation may be the low concentrations of the four VOCs within the mixture. Additionally, more recent studies compared

sebum of PD patients and healthy people. Overall, studies agree that there is a difference in the sebum composition. However, which VOCs are responsible for this change is less clear [8–10]. Interestingly, one study was able to predict PD from the odor profile of sebum with 79 % accuracy using an artificial intelligent olfactory system [10].

One limitation of this study is that it is unclear which VOCs are responsible for the difference between sebum of PD patients and healthy people [3,8,9]. Of note, three of the VOCs were higher and one was lower in PD sebum compared to healthy sebum, therefore it would be interesting to also include a sample using only these three VOCs. Furthermore, although the patient's wife reported that these three VOCs have a similar smell to the PD BO [3], additional VOCs appear to be of significance. Another limitation is the solubility of the VOCs. In our study, 1,2-propanediol, a solvent commonly used in human olfaction research, was used. However, it may not be the best one for all four VOCs. In future studies the possibility of using different solvents for each compound might be explored. Furthermore, highly sensitive nanomaterials-based electronic nose may be explored to discriminate the artificial PD BO from the healthy BO for further use in the early diagnosis of PD [11,12]. Another possible limitation is that healthy BO donors did not undergo olfactory testing which might have resulted in the inclusion of a person in early phases of PD. Furthermore, direct comparison of the healthy BO and PD BO should be investigated and further studies on a bigger sample are needed to confirm the results from this pilot study.

In conclusion, this study showed that young women perceive the BO of PD patients as different in quality compared to healthy BO or artificial PD BO. However, the four VOCs, used for the artificial PD BO, were insufficient to reproduce it. These results support the previous finding that the sebum of PD patients differs from the sebum of healthy people [3,8–10], indicating that the phenotype of PD goes beyond the dopaminergic and motor systems. In the future, this difference could potentially be used to screen for PD patients using highly sensitive nanomaterials-based electronic nose (e-nose) [11,12].

Data availability

Data and code are available upon request on: <https://doi.org/10.7303/syn53278108>.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Eva Drnovsek: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Alexandra Parichenko:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Conceptualization. **Nicole Power Guerra:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Conceptualization. **Julia Pabst:** Methodology, Investigation. **Kristof Wunderlich:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology,

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare the following financial interests/personal relationships which may be considered as potential competing interests: Since 2021 TH has collaborated on research projects with Sony, Stuttgart, Germany; Smell and Taste Lab, Geneva, Switzerland; Takasago, Paris, France; asparaclip, Berlin, Germany. He received consultancy fees from Baia Foods, Madrid, Spain; Burghart, Holm, Germany; air-up, Munich, Germany. Other authors declare that they have no conflict of interest.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.parkreldis.2024.107091>.

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